

Numerical algorithm to reproduce Turing pattern figures

Description:

Pseudocode to reproduce figures 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 22, 23 of manuscript number **EPJS-D-25-00637R3**.

The parameter set used in this analysis is given in the manuscript.

Pseudocode 3 Turing Pattern Formation

- 1: **Input:** Model parameters $(b, d_1, r, K, K_1, \beta, b_2, b_3, e, d_2, h, \alpha)$ and diffusion coefficients (d_H, d_P)
 - 2: **Input:** Spatial domain (l_x, l_y) , grid sizes (n_x, n_y) , time step Δt , final time T
 - 3: Compute spatial step size $\Delta x = l_x / (n_x - 1)$
 - 4: Set total number of time steps $N_t = T / \Delta t$
 - 5: Generate uniform spatial grids $x \in [0, l_x]$ and $y \in [0, l_y]$
 - 6: Initialize prey density $H(x, y, 0)$ with small random perturbations
 - 7: Initialize predator density $P(x, y, 0)$ with small random perturbations
 - 8: Specify discrete output times for storing solution snapshots
 - 9: **for** $n = 1$ to N_t **do**
 - 10: Compute Laplacians $\nabla^2 H$ and $\nabla^2 P$ using second-order finite differences
 - 11: Impose zero-flux (Neumann) boundary conditions on all boundaries
 - 12: Evaluate nonlinear reaction terms for prey and predator populations
 - 13: Update prey density:
$$H^{n+1} = H^n + \Delta t (\text{reaction}_H + d_H \nabla^2 H)$$
 - 14: Update predator density:
$$P^{n+1} = P^n + \Delta t (\text{reaction}_P + d_P \nabla^2 P)$$
 - 15: Enforce non-negativity:
$$H^{n+1} = \max(H^{n+1}, 0), \quad P^{n+1} = \max(P^{n+1}, 0)$$
 - 16: Store H^{n+1} and P^{n+1} at prescribed output times
 - 17: **end for**
 - 18: **Output:** Spatial distributions of prey and predator densities at selected times
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